

“POLYHERBAL DIGESTIVE AVALEHA”

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Abstract : Avaleha is a traditional ayurvedic confession, offers a palatable and effective method for delivering herbal remedies. This formulation combine aegle maemelos (bael fruit), cummins (jeera), ajwain (carom seeds), and amala (Indian gooseberry). Each known for its digestive benefits. Aegle marmelos is traditionally used for managing diarrhea and dysentery and acts as a digestive aid. Cumin stimulates digestive enzyme and reduces bloating. ajwain relieves gas, acidity and promote regular bowel moment.

Keywords: Polyherbal Digestive Avaleha

INTRODUCTION

Digestion is about a lot more than simply what you eat. From the standpoint of Ayurveda, digestion is broadly defined as “anything that is taken in from any field of perception, thought, any sense of preparation, any mode of mind, and any mode of intellect.”

When you eat something, it goes on a complex journey through your body. From a western perspective, it takes about six to eight hours for food to pass from the stomach to your small intestine. After that, the partially digested food enters your large intestine (colon), where it spends another 36 hours moving along for further digestion and absorption of water before being eliminated.

From ayurvedic perspective, the complete and more subtle digestive process takes around 36 days and ends with the production of something called ojas. The finest byproduct of digestion. Ojas means “life essence,” or that which supports good health and longevity.

According to the Sushruta Samhita—an ancient ayurvedic text—healthy digestion comes from balanced doshas (mind-body energies), balanced agni (digestive fire), balanced dhatus (bodily tissues), balanced malas (wastes), and a well-coordinated and alert state of self (atma), senses (indriyas), and mind (manas).

Avaleha is a traditional ayurvedic dosage form, often referred to as a herbal jamor electuary. It is prepared by processing medicinal herbs with jaggery or sugar, ghee, and honey to form a thick, semi-solid paste. Avaleha are widely used in Ayurveda for their palatability, prolonged shelf-life, and ease of administration.

Digestive avaleha refers to a specific type of avaleha formulation aimed at supporting and improving the digestive system. These preparations typically contain herbs with **deepana** (

appetizer) and **pachana** (digestive) properties. Common ingredient include **pippali** (long paper) , **ginger** (shunthi), **haritaki**, **trikatu** ,and **jeeraka** (cumin) , among others.

What is digestive avaleha ?

Avaleha are traditional ayurvedic formulations known for their palatability and therapeutics benefits. They are typically made by simmering herbal decoction with jaggery and sometimes honey until they achieve a thick, sticky consistency. These preparations are used to support digestive health, alleviate discomfort, and promote overall gastrointestinal well-being.

Amla Fruit:

Synonyms : emblica , Indian goose berry amla .

Biological Source :

This consist dried, as well as fresh fruit the plant emblica officinalis gaerth (Phyllanthus emblica linn), belonging to family euphorbiaceace. Geographical source : it is a small- or medium-sized tree found in all deciduous forests in india.

It is also found in sri lanka and Myanmar. The leaves are feathery with small oblong pinnately arranged leaflets. The tree is characteristic greenish-grey and with smooth bark.

It highly nutritious and is an important dietary source of vitamin c , minerals, and amino acids. The fruit also contains considerably higher concentration of most minerals and amino acids than apples. The pulpy portion of fruit , dried and freed from the nuts contains: gallic acid , tannin, sugar, gum, albumin, crude, cellulose, mineral matter, and moisture.

Fig. Amla (Indian gooseberry)

Bael fruit :

Synonyms: bael fruit , bel Bengal quince, belan.

Biological source: bael consist of the unripe or half-ripe fruit or their slices/pieces of aegle marmelos corr., belonging to family rutaceae.

Geographical source : sub- Himalaya tract and throughout india, especially central and southern india occurring as wild cultivated.

Chemical constituents :

The chief constituent of the drug is marmelosin A, B and C (0.5%). Which is a further other coumarins are marmesin, psoralen and umbelliferone. The drug also carbohydrate (11-17%), protein, volatile oil and tannins. The pulp also con. Amount of vitamins C and A.

Bael has a long history of use in traditional medicine due to its divers health benefits. In addition to its medicinal properties , the fruit is also consumed fresh or in various culinary preparations, such as juices , jams and preserves.

One of the most well-known properties of bael fruit is its beneficial effects on digestion . here's how its works.

Fiber content: Bael fruit is rich in dietary fibre, including both soluble and insoluble fiber. This fiber content helps promote regular bowel movements and prevents constipation by adding bulk to the stool.

Tannins: Bael contain tannins, which are a type of polyphenolic compound. Tannins have astringent properties, which can help in the treatment of diarrhea by reducing intestinal inflammation and tightening the mucous membranes.

Digestive enzymes: Bael fruit contains enzymes like pectinase, which aid in the breakdown of complex carbohydrates into simpler sugars , facilitating digestion. These enzymes can also help alleviate symptoms of indigestion and bloating.

Antimicrobial activity: Bael fruit exhibits antimicrobial properties, which can help in the treatment of gastrointestinal infections caused by bacteria or parasites. By inhibiting the growth of harmful micro-organisms, bael can support overall digestive health.

Cumin, scientifically known as *cuminum cyminum*, is a flowering plant native to the eastern Mediterranean region and southwestern asia. It has been cultivated for thousand of year and is highly value for both culinary and medicinal purposes. Cumin seeds, which come from the plant's dried fruit, are widely used as a spice in various cuisines around the world.

Cumin is removed for its digestive properties and has been used for centuries to alleviate digestive discomfort and promote overall digestive health.

Aloe vera is often referred to as the “ plant of immortality” due to its resilience and the myriad of health benefits it offers . the gel obtain from its leaves is widely used in traditional medicine skincare products , and dietary supplements. Aloe vera gel is rich in bioactive compounds, including vitamins , minerals, amino acids , polysaccharides, and antioxidants, which contribute to its healing properties .

Aloe vera gel contains compounds like polysaccharides, glycoproteins, and amino acids that possess anti-inflammatory and wound healing properties.

medicinal purpose. In ancient times, ajwain was included in recipes to aid digestion as it has carminative properties.

Ajwain has numerous uses, primarily for its digestive and respiratory benefits. It is often used to aid digestion, relieve bloating and indigestion, and combat respiratory ailments like cough, asthma, and bronchitis.

Fig : bael fruit

fig : cumin

DISCUSSION :

The uses of polyherbal formulation like digestive avaleha has been an integral part of traditional ayurvedic medicines for managing various gastrointestinal ailments. Avaleha preparation is characterized by their semisolid consistency and palatable nature, offering a convenient and effective medium for the administration of multiple herbal ingredients. The action of its components, each contributing specific digestive, carminative, or laxative properties.

Overall, digestive avaleha represents a promising herbal remedy for digestive health, warranting further scientific exploration to establish a clearer evidence base for its clinical use.

CONCLUSION:

The review of the polyherbal digestive avaleha highlights its potential as an effective traditional formulation for supporting digestive health. Comprising synergistic blends of medicinal herbs, this preparation exhibits properties such as appetizing, carminative, and mild laxative actions, contributing to the management of common gastrointestinal disturbances like indigestion and

constipation. Future research integrating modern scientific validation with traditional ayurvedic knowledge can enhance its therapeutic application and global acceptance.

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